

(REVIEW ARTICLE)

How leadership, work motivation effect on employee work discipline

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Abstract

This research aims to determine the effect of leadership and work motivation on employee work discipline at Bank BPD Bali Mangupura Branch. The population in this study was 115 employees. To obtain data, researchers used a questionnaire distributed to employees. The analysis technique used is multiple linear regression analysis. The results of this research show that the Leadership Variable does not have a positive effect on work discipline and work motivation has a positive effect on discipline. Leadership and work motivation variables together have a positive effect on work discipline.

Keywords: Leadership; Work Motivation; Work discipline; Employee; Bank

1. Introduction

According to Darwati & Soegiarto (2011), work discipline is a "punishment", even though the real meaning is not that. Discipline comes from the Latin "*Disciplina*" which means training or education in politeness and spirituality as well as character development. So the nature of discipline is related to the development of a proper attitude towards work. According to (Nurjaya & Riswan, 2019) Leadership is an action that effect other people or subordinates to want to work together to achieve certain goals. Motivation is one of the things that effect human behavior. Motivation is also called a driver, desire, supporter or needs that can make someone enthusiastic and motivated to reduce and fulfill their own urges (Shakespeare, 2014).

With many problems occurring where customers feel that the service provided is not in accordance with Standard Operating Procedures, this problem is based on the public's negative view of service, for example poor service and inadequate service conditions for customers. During my research, I saw a lack of cooperation between leaders and employees, a lack of motivation given by leaders to employees, resulting in a lack of work discipline among Bank BPD Bali Mangupura Branch.

The aim to be achieved in the research is to find out how much effect leadership and work motivation have on the work discipline of employees at Bank BPD Bali Mangupura Branch and to find out how much effect leadership and work motivation simultaneously have on the work discipline of employees at Bank BPD Bali Mangupura Branch. The reason that drives researchers' interest in discussing this is that the existence of leadership and work motivation apparently has an effect that can improve employee work discipline.

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2. Literature review and hypothesis development

Previous research conducted by (Saletti-cuesta et al., 2020) explained in his research entitled The effect of leadership and motivation on Civil Service (PNS) work discipline in the Blitar Regency Livestock and Fisheries Service. The results show that leadership has a positive and significant effect on the work discipline of civil servants (PNS) in the Livestock and Fisheries Service. And work motivation has no positive and insignificant effect on the work discipline of Civil Servants (PNS) in the Livestock and Fisheries Service.

Previous research conducted by (Rahayu, 2021) explained in his research entitled The effect of leadership style and motivation on employee work discipline at the Deputy for Youth Development at the Ministry of Youth and Sports. The results show that leadership style has a positive and significant effect on work discipline. Motivation has an effect on work discipline.

Previous research conducted by (Puspitasari et al., 2017) explained in his research entitled The Effect of leadership style, compensation and work environment on employee work discipline (Study in Regional Drinking Water Company (PDAM) Lawu Tirta, Magetan Regency). The research results show that leadership style has a significant effect on the work discipline of PDAM Lawu Tirta employees, Magetan Regency. Compensation has a significant effect on the work discipline of PDAM Lawu Tirta employees, Magetan Regency. The work environment has a partial and significant effect on work discipline. Based on this description, the hypothesis in this research is as follows:

H1: Leadership has a positive and significant effect on the work discipline

Previous research carried out by Darwati & Soegiarto (2011) regarding the effect of leadership on the work discipline of civil servants at the West Kutai Regency Regional Civil Service Agency. The research results show that leadership has a positive and significant effect on work discipline.

H2: Work motivation has a positive and significant effect on work discipline

3. Methods

The aim of this research is to determine the effect of leadership and work motivation on employee work discipline at Bank BPD Bali Mangupura Branch, so this research is quantitative in nature. The research data is quantitative data. In this model, research is carried out by researchers distributing questionnaires to obtain data for research. In this research, the independent variables used are leadership and work motivation variables, while the dependent variable is the work discipline variable.

Sugiyono (2017) Quantitative research methods are based on the philosophy of positivism, used to research certain populations or samples, data collection using research instruments, data analysis is quantitative or statistical, with the aim of testing predetermined hypotheses. The variables whose relationship will be studied and the aim is to present an overview of the relationship between the leadership variables studied.

According to Adityatama (2019) leadership indicators are: 1) Having a clear business strategy, 2) Providing attention and motivating members' work,

3) Invite all members to be quality oriented, 4) Invite members to work in a solid and harmonious team, 5) Resolve any conflicts between members well. The word lead contains the meaning of directing, building or managing, guiding and also showing or influencing. Leaders have both physical and spiritual effect on the success of the work activities of those they lead, so being a leader does not ready and will not be loyal, people have similarities in carrying out their leadership Darwati & Soegiarto (2011)

Motivation comes from the Latin word *movere* which means encouragement, driving force or force that causes an action or deed. The word *movere*, in English, is often equated with motivation, which means giving motives, generating motives, or things that give rise to encouragement or circumstances that give rise to encouragement (Hastuti, 2016). According to Adityatama (2019) indicators of work motivation are: 1) engagement; 2) commitment; 3) satisfaction; 4) turnover.

Rofifah (2020) Work discipline is a set of rules or regulations made by the management of an organization, ratified by the board of commissioners or capital owners, agreed upon by the labor union and known by the labor service so that

people who join the organization are subject to the rules. existing order with pleasure. Regarding indicators of work discipline in this research, taken according to the views of (Aini, 2020), they are: 1) punctuality; 2) use office equipment properly; 3) high responsibility; 4) compliance with office rules.

The relationship between each variable which states that leadership and work motivation effect employee work discipline. For this reason, researchers want to examine the simultaneous effect that leadership and work motivation have on employee work discipline. The population in this research is the population, namely 115 employees of Bank BPD Mangupura Branch. The data analysis technique used is multiple linear regression analysis technique.

4. Results and discussion

4.1. Validity test

Uji Validity is used to measure whether a questionnaire is valid or not (Gunawan & Sunardi, 2016). A questionnaire is said to be valid if the results of the correlation have a significance level of less than 0.05 (5%). The measurement scale is said to be valid if it is able to measure according to the indicators of the statements in the research. If the measurement scale is invalid then it is not useful for researchers because it cannot measure indicators of the variable. The results of the data validity test can be shown in the following table:

Table 1 Validity Test Results

Variable	Item	r-value	r table	Result
Work Discipline Y	Y.1	0.589	0.252	Valid
	Y.2	0.668	0.252	Valid
	Y.3	0.612	0.252	Valid
	Y.4	0.675	0.252	Valid
	Y.5	0.621	0.252	Valid
	Y.6	0.618	0.252	Valid
Leadership X1	X1.1	0.486	0.252	Valid
	X1.2	0.604	0.252	Valid
	X1.3	0.774	0.252	Valid
	X1.4	0.785	0.252	Valid
	X1.5	0.825	0.252	Valid
	X1.6	0.893	0.252	Valid
	X1.7	0.892	0.252	Valid
	X1.8	0.874	0.252	Valid
	X1.9	0.857	0.252	Valid
	X1.10	0.856	0.252	Valid
Work Motivation X2	X2.1	0.931	0.252	Valid
	X2.2	0.963	0.252	Valid
	X2.3	0.964	0.252	Valid
	X2.4	0.875	0.252	Valid

Primary Data, 2024

Based on the results of the validity test with a total of 61 respondents, it can be seen that all statements regarding leadership, work motivation and work discipline submitted to respondents from Bank BPD Mangupura Branch employees are valid because seen from the level of $r \text{ count} > r \text{ table}$, this is shown in the person correlation value. is

above the r-table above the r-table or more than 0.252 and the significance is below 0.05. So it can be concluded that all the statements in the questionnaire can be said to be suitable as instruments for measuring research data.

4.2. Reliability Test

Reliability is the degree of precision, precision or accuracy displayed by the measurement tool that has been used. A questionnaire can be said to be reliable if the results of a person's answers to questions are consistent or stable over time (Sugiyono, 2017).

Table 2 Reliability test results

Variable	Cronbach's Alpha	Information
Work discipline	0.781	Reliable
Leadership	0.781	Reliable
Work Motivation	0.848	Reliable

Primary Data, 2024

What was done after showing that all the statement variables were worthy of being used as research instruments was to carry out a large sample test of 115 respondents. A statement can be said to be reliable if the Cronbach's Alpha value is >0.600 . The following are reliable test results. Based on the table above, it can be concluded that the questionnaire that has been distributed is a reliable questionnaire because the Cronbach's Alpha value is > 0.600 . The value of the Leadership variable is $0.781 > 0.600$, the Work Motivation variable is $0.848 > 0.600$ and for Work Discipline $0.781 > 0.600$.

4.3. Partial test results (t test)

Ujit is used to find out whether the independent variables partially have a real effect on the dependent variable or not. The degree of significance used is 0.05. If the significant value is smaller than the degree of confidence then we accept the alternative hypothesis, which states that an independent variable partially effect the dependent variable. The t statistical test basically shows how much effect an independent variable partially has in explaining the dependent variable.

Table 3 t-test

Variable	Unstandardized coefficients		Std coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	23.881	6.062		3.939	0.00
Leadership	-0.319	0.124	-0.179	-2.458	0.113
Work Motivation	0.529	0.080	0.549	3.695	0.000
F test = 52.989 F Sig = 0.000					

Primary Data, 2024

Based on the t statistical test, the calculated t value is -2.574 and a significant value of 0.003. If seen from the comparison of t calculated with t table (t calculated $>$ t table) the calculated t value is known to be greater than the t table value ($2.574 > 2.002$) and the significance value is greater than 0.05 ($0.013 > 0.05$). The research hypothesis states that leadership has no positive effect on employee work discipline and has no significant effect on employee work discipline H1. So it can be concluded that the Leadership variable has no positive effect on employee work discipline.

Based on the t statistical test, the calculated t value is 3.695 and a significant value of 0.000. If seen from the comparison of t calculated with t table (t calculated $>$ t table) the calculated t value is known to be greater than the t table value ($3.695 > 2.002$) and the significance value is smaller than 0.05 ($0.000 < 0.05$). The research hypothesis states that work

motivation has a positive effect on employee work discipline and has a significant effect on employee work discipline H2. So, it can be concluded that the work motivation variable has a positive effect on employee work discipline.

F-test is carried out to test the effect of the independent variable and the dependent variable simultaneously so that this research model is fit. If the significant value is <0.05 , then the independent variable effects the dependent variable and the independent variable is suitable to be used to predict the dependent variable. Based on research results, it is known that the independent variables Leadership, and Work Motivation have a simultaneous effect on Work Discipline. This can be seen from the results of the statistical test f . If we look at the significant value of f , it is 0.000 which is smaller than $\alpha = 0.05$ ($0.000 < 0.05$). so it can be concluded that there is an effect of leadership and work motivation simultaneously effect on employee work discipline because the significance value is $0.00 < 0.05$.

5. Conclusion

Based on data analysis and hypothesis testing results in this research, it can be concluded that leadership has no positive effect and no significant effect on employee work discipline because the significance level is $0.013 > 0.05$; work motivation has a positive and significant effect on work discipline because the significance level is $0.000 < 0.05$; leadership and work motivation have a simultaneous effect on employee work discipline, if seen from the results of the f test which explains that there is a simultaneous/joint effect of leadership and work motivation on employee work discipline. So, the researchers concluded that leadership and work motivation simultaneously effect employee work discipline.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest to be disclosed.

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